

DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE ECONOMISTS BASED ON INNOVATIVE APPROACHES

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Annotation: The formation of professional competences of modern economists requires from the educational institution, from the teachers fundamentally new approaches in professional education: the integration of pedagogical, economic and entrepreneurial knowledge, skills and abilities. The aim of the study is to analyze modern approaches to the formulation of the concept of »competence«, to find out the components of professional competence for the preparation of future economists.

Key words: competence, competency approach, professional competence, economist, educational process.

Today, in modern conditions, the wide use of the achievements of world science and innovation activities is becoming an important factor in the consistent and stable development of all spheres of society and state life, as well as in building a worthy future of our country. Because in today's era of rapid development, society needs qualified specialists who think actively, create innovative ideas and effectively apply them in practice. This, in turn, requires the development of innovative educational programs that help to improve the quality of education by introducing innovations, modern interactive and creative methods of teaching and directing them to the field, organizing and managing scientific research of the leaders and pedagogues of higher educational institutions, and developing their innovative competence.

Currently, the renewal of education is not only the implementation of the development of State educational standards, but through the educational process in higher education institutions, the mindset of students who can clearly imagine their future, have a conscious attitude to their destiny and their personality, and develop themselves in various activities has been formed. , envisages the formation of a free, active and independent person. When teaching economic subjects to students and forming their economic thinking, it is always necessary to organize lessons from the point of view of nationality and national interests. It is necessary to rely on objectivity and justice in studying and evaluating the level of economic development and the system of economic relations of each era.

In the conditions of modern globalization, as we are shaping the national economy, we must deliver economic education that teaches a new system of economic relations that is forming in the minds of students, harmonizing it with our national values, for this, we must prepare economic science textbooks and manuals for higher education institutions at the level of world standards and without forgetting nationality. we should note separately. For this, we need to realize that economic relations characteristic of the market did not appear yesterday in the history of our statehood, on the contrary, its emergence goes back to a long history.

Education of new independent thinking and creative students remains one of our main problems in higher education. During the student years, young people rise to the stage of biological maturity, social maturity, and physical strength. In students, important aspects of intelligence such as self-control, self-evaluation, self-awareness, and self-management will rise to a new high level of development. General professional and specialized sciences play an important role in the development of thinking and the formation of a scientific outlook.

Students' thinking develops intensively and continuously mainly in reading, practical training and independent learning activities. Sometimes the lecture process requires reproductive thinking from them, but practical exercises, independent assignments, and laboratory assignments require productive (creative) thinking. Both forms of education are realized with the help of students' mental work, goal-oriented and coordinated attention. In the course of education, theoretical, practical and methodological foundations of modern economy, deep theoretical methodological, scientific-methodical knowledge of entrepreneurship and business laws are mastered. Especially in this period, thinking acts as an effective intelligence tool for the student.

The subjects taught in higher education institutions consist of a system of tasks and problems of a problematic nature that require continuous creative thinking. Each lecture, seminar, independent study, laboratory work will be composed of components of a problem situation. Solving them requires creative research from the student. Because the period before the problem situation, the problem situation, and the mental processes after the problem situation also require the student to carry out creative search and research activities. Independent performance of tasks requires students to use thinking operations (analysis, comparison, comparison, abstraction, generalization, grouping) and forms (concept, judgment, conclusion).

In our opinion, the role of the student's independence in the process of problem-based teaching of economics is more effective than in reproductive teaching methods. The purpose of problem-based education is that professors and teachers are able to arouse interest in students in the process of working with students in the search for answers to educational issues, problems and questions that arise, assimilating new knowledge with ways to solve them, creating and solving problematic situations in students' educational activities. . Including:

1. Analyzing and thinking about the problems that have arisen in the economy is one of the important requirements for the development of independent mental activity of students. Such thinking makes the student realize that he could not understand this thing, and focuses on seriously paying attention to the meaning of this sentence and forming his thinking.

2. It is necessary to make economic thinking a part of the basis of the educational process and educational work in order to make economic thinking effective and suitable for the purpose of teaching in higher education institutions. With the help of problem-based education, future economists are trained to develop the research approach to solving educational problems and specialized issues, develop economic thinking, and develop the ability to learn independently.

3. Economic education helps students to effectively master knowledge systems and intellectual and practical activities, to form their thinking, to be able to effectively use the acquired knowledge in future situations, to solve educational problems, to teach independent research, to have creative experience and to develop it, to analyze the tasks of the educational process does, opens up opportunities to identify problematic learning.

Creating a multi-sector economy in our country, implementing structural changes in the economy indicated in the Action Strategy for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, i.e. not only implementing economic reforms, but also forming a new economic mindset in people, especially young people, plays an important role. Because economic thinking is the basis for society members to learn to think independently and make decisions according to the situation.

The fourth direction of the strategy of actions called "Development of the social sphere" envisages the improvement of the quality of higher education and the implementation of measures for their development. Preparing students for independent education and self-development in

higher education institutions of economics is one of the urgent problems. For this, it is appropriate to use various teaching technologies during training:

- Forming the integrity of educational activities and logical thinking in students.
- Activation of students' independent learning activities.
- Formation of thinking characteristics to develop logical thinking in students.
- Development of students' dialectical thinking in the process of training.
- Formation of creative thinking in students in the process of passing new economic sciences such as "Digital Economy", "Economy of Knowledge", "Innovative Economy", etc.

In general, in higher educational institutions of economics, such teaching, which is aimed at forming the thinking of students during the educational process, helps them to realize themselves and develop themselves. In this case, education is perceived by students not as a goal to be achieved, but as a means of personal development, and in the course of training, their interest in economic education increases.

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